

An application of the DHI Methodology for a Comparison of SARS-CoV-2 Epidemic Hazards in Customer Delivery Services of Smart Cities

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Supplementary Materials

Scales of potential virus transmission mechanisms in transportation services

The first step of the methodology was to determine all potential virus transmission mechanisms in transport services. In accordance with the assumed goal, possible mechanisms of SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus infection were identified as methods of virus transmission between participants of the transport process, taking into account the droplet transmission and contact by the infected surfaces transmission. Value scaling was performed according to the current knowledge and epidemic characteristics of the biological hazards of SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. Based on an in-depth study of the issue for specific transport services, the following factors determining the mechanisms of infection were defined:

Based on these knowledge the scale of hazards as distance of contact with another person for the mechanism of infection by droplets have been developed.

Table 1. Scale of hazards – social distance with another person for the mechanism of infection by droplets

Hazard score	Description
1	Direct contact with another person at a distance of more than 6.5 meters.
2	Direct contact with another person from 3 meters to 6.5 meters.
3	Direct contact with another person from 1.5 meters to 3 meters.
4	Direct contact with another person within 0.5 meters to 1.5 meters.
5	Direct contact with another person within 0.5 meters

Droplets person-to-person transmission of SARS-CoV-2 is probably most important factor, but it may be also transmitted to a new host through infected surfaces. Coronavirus has the capability of staying for longer durations on various surfaces (Mukhra et al., 2020). Therefore, SARS-CoV-2 can be transmitted via indirect contact with the surfaces contaminated by the infected person.

The second important for the transport processes virus transmission mechanism is surface or skin contact. For this purpose, calculations were made taking into account the number of people participating in the transport process (passengers or operators) at the same time in a specific time interval in the means of transport. Such assumptions make it possible to estimate the probability of touching the same pieces of equipment on the vehicle, so the probability of virus transmission by surface contact.

Table 2. Scale of hazards - threats of touching an infected surface in the means of transport

Hazard score	Description
1	Direct use of the infrastructure or interior of the vehicle within an hour by one person or disinfection after each user.
2	Direct use of the infrastructure or the interior of the vehicle within an hour of less than 10 people.
3	Direct use of the infrastructure or the interior of the vehicle within an hour from 10 people to 99.
4	Direct use of the infrastructure or the interior of the vehicle within an hour from 100 to 150 people.
5	Direct use of the infrastructure or interior of the vehicle for more than 150 people or a high probability of contact of an infected person.

Another criterion of epidemic risk in transport processes is the time during which the transported cargo (goods) was in close distance to the potentially infected person. The mean arm range of an adult's was assumed as the close distance. In this case, there is a risk of leaving a biological trace on the load, both by droplets and by touch. For scaling, time intervals were assumed, assuming the probability of leaving a biological trace multiple times increasing in time. Taking into account that the time for spreading the aerosol for about 1.75 meters when sneezing is about 4.5 seconds and the aerosol, depending on the size of the particles, falls to the surface after about 10 minutes, and it can stay in the air for up to 30 minutes. Based on studies of Dental Societies it was assumed that a significant increase in the risk of infection occurs after 15 minutes.

Table 3. Scale of hazards – the time the load (goods) is in close distance of a potentially infected person.

Hazard score	Description
1	The load has been in close proximity to a potential infected person for less than 5 seconds or has been disinfected.
2	The load have been in the vicinity of a potential infected person for less than 10 minutes or have been disinfected
3	The load were kept for 10 to 15 minutes in the close vicinity of a potential infected person
4	The load were kept for 15 to 30 minutes in the close vicinity of a potential infected person
5	The load have been in the vicinity of a potential infected person for more than 30 minutes

Another risk factor for infection is the time during which the cargo (load) in transport remains without contact with a potential source of infection (humans). In this case, the time during which the SARS-CoV-2 virus can persist on different surfaces was analyzed (table 5).

Table 4. Time duration the virus remains on infected surfaces, based on (Mukhra et al., 2020) and (Patients et al., 2020)

Material of surface	Time duration of infection stay
Aerosols	Approximately 3 hours
Copper	Not more than 4 hours
Cardboard	Not more than 24 hours
Plastic, Stainless steel	Up to 72 hours

Table 5. Scale of hazards - time during which the load in transit remains without contact with a potential source of infection

Hazard score	Description
1	The loads, after potential infection, were immediately disinfected.
2	Potentially infected loads were either isolated from people for more than 72 hours or disinfected.
3	After potential infection, the loads were isolated from people for 24 to 48 hours.
4	After the possible infection, the loads were isolated from people for less than 24 hours
5	After the possible infection, the loads were not isolated.

Similarly to the risk of infection by contact with the infected surface, the criteria for evaluation were adopted in relation to the time after which the vehicle was reused or disinfected.

Table 6. Scale of hazards - time during between mean of transport were used for the next time after the potential source of infection

Hazard score	Description
1	After the possible contamination, the vehicle was either isolated for more than 72 hours or disinfected after each transport service performed.
2	After the possible contamination, the vehicle was isolated for 72 to 48 hours and was not disinfected.

3	After the possible contamination, the vehicle was isolated for 48 to 24 hours and was not disinfected.
4	The potentially infected vehicle has been isolated for less than 24 hours and has not been disinfected.
5	After the potential contamination, the vehicle has not been isolated from people and has not been disinfected.

SARS-CoV-2 virus, as air-transmittable viruses are emitted from an infected individual during coughing, sneezing, talking, or even breathing, and that it can stay in the air in a confined room for up to 30 minutes (García De Abajo et al., 2020). For this reason, as another criterion, a measure linking the exposure time and the number of people in the means of transport between disinfection activities was formulated.

Table 7. Scale of hazards - exposure time and the number of people in the means of transport between disinfection operations

Hazard score	Description
1	The mean of transport has been disinfected after each use.
2	The mean of transport has been used for less than 15 minutes by less than 10 people or has been disinfected.
3	The mean of transport has been used for more than 15 minutes by more than 10 people.
4	The mean of transport has been used for more than 30 minutes for less than 10 people.
5	The mean of transport has been used for more than 30 minutes by more than 10 people.

When analyzing the factors of epidemic threats in transport, not only passengers should be considered, but also employees (operators) in transport, both in the passenger and freight transport. Based on the current knowledge (García De Abajo et al., 2020) (Shafaghi et al., 2020a) and pandemic work place recommendations, the following rating scale has been defined.

Table 8. Scale of hazards - potential infection depending on worker (operator) exposure time

Hazard score	Description
1	The employee was less than 10 minutes in the vicinity of the potentially infected person.
2	The employee was kept from 10 to 15 minutes at a distance of 6.5 to 2 meters from a potential infected person
3	The employee was more than 15 minutes away from a possible infected person between 6.5 and 2 meters.
4	The employee has been kept for 10 to 15 minutes less than 2 meters from a potential infected person.
5	The employee has been more than 15 minutes less than 2 meters from a potential infected person

The time of exposure to potential biological hazards is so important that it was decided to additionally develop a criterion related to travel time. This criterion will be particularly important in individual transport services, including taxi and car-sharing.

Table 9. Scale of hazards – travel (transportation) time

Hazard score	Description
1	Transport takes place only with the participation of one driver
2	Less than 10 minutes
3	From 10 minutes to 30 minutes
4	From 30 minutes to 1 hour
5	Over an hour

Social distancing is important for the protection against COVID-19 but not only for outdoor spaces but even more important for indoor spaces, including means of transport. Therefore as the next criterion the distance between seats and space per passenger have been taken. 1.5m was assumed as a safe distance. Therefore, the unit of measurement in this criterion was 1.5 m as the distance between the available seats and the area of the circle with a radius of 1.5 m, i.e. approx. 7.1 m².

Table 10. Scale of hazards – potential for infection depending on the distance between the seats and the space of the vehicle per passenger

Hazard score	Description
1	Transportation takes place without passengers. Only the driver is in the vehicle
2	Each participant of the transportation has at least 7.1 m ² of space and the distance of the seats is not less than 1.5 meters
3	Each participant of the transportation has at least 7.1 m ² of space and the distance between the seats is less than 1.5 meters
4	Each participant of the transportation has less than 7.1 m ² of space and the distance of the seats is not less than 1.5 meters
5	Each participant has less than 7.1 m ² of space and the distance between the seats is less than 1.5 meters

In the case of the analysis of collective urban transport, but also courier parcels, an important factor of epidemic hazards are also the dynamics and frequency of passenger exchange (or the potential contact of the courier while delivering the parcel). This is due to the probabilities of contact with another infected person.

Table 11. Scale of hazards – the frequency and number of stops (delivery points)

Hazard score	Description
1	No stops (delivery) during the transport service, except for the initial and final stops
2	The time between stops (delivery) is over 30 minutes

3	The time between stops (delivery) is 10 to 30 minutes
4	The time between stops (delivery) is 5 to 10 minutes
5	The time between stops (delivery) is less than 5 minutes

It can be assumed that in the same manner, air flow could transfer and deposit infected respiratory droplets/nuclei from infected persons to the mucous membranes of persons standing against the air flow direction (Rule, 2020) (Lu et al., 2020) (Mouchtouri et al., 2020). Interior of mean of transport complex flows form due to the presence of recirculatory flows driven by ventilation systems and anthropogenic thermally driven flow effects (Shafaghi et al., 2020a). Therefore, the circulation and exchange of air in the means of transport were adopted as another factor of the epidemic hazard.

Table 12. Scale of hazards – possible infection depending on air circulation and exchange and air conditioning

Hazard score	Description
1	The air circulation in an open circuit runs through HEPA filters
2	Continuous and smooth air exchange in the vehicle through open-circuit ventilation and opening windows
3	Air exchange in the vehicle by means of open circuit ventilation or opening windows
4	Open circuit air conditioning
5	Air conditioning and air exchange operating in a closed circuit

In the case of freight transportation, the loading and unloading process is very often overlooked in various analyzes. From the point of view of epidemic threats, this process is very important because it may involve direct contact between people or the possibility of infecting the surface of the cargo. Therefore, in order to comprehensively analyze all hazards, an assessment scale for loading and unloading activities was also developed.

Table 13. Scale of hazards – potential infection depending on the type of loading and unloading

Hazard score	Description
1	Loading or unloading takes place without contact. The driver remains in the vehicle cabin and has no contact with the service that performs loading or unloading activities, or with the loads
2	Loading or unloading takes place without contact. The driver is responsible for unloading or loading. There is no contact with the service, but there is contact with the loads
3	Loading or unloading takes place with the participation of both the driver and the staff and takes less than 10 minutes
4	Loading or unloading takes place with the participation of both the driver and the staff and takes 10 to 30 minutes

5	Loading or unloading takes place with the participation of both the driver and the staff and takes more than 30 minutes
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Another potential source of infection are the activities related to preparation and securing the load. There is a risk of contact between operators in transport (droplet transmission) or leaving a microbial trace on the surface (contact infection). For this purpose, a descriptive scale has also been developed.

Table 14. Scale of hazards –potential infection depending on the preparation and securing of the cargo

Hazard score	Description
1	Preparation and securing of the load takes place without contact between the driver and the loader, loading is carried out by one person and the driver has no contact with the load
2	Preparation and securing of the load takes place without contact between the driver and the loader, loading is carried out by more than one person and the driver has no contact with the load
3	Preparing and securing the load takes place without contact between the driver and the loader, while the driver has direct contact with the load
4	The preparation and securing of the load takes place both with the participation of the driver and a maximum of one operator
5	The preparation and securing of the load takes place both with the participation of the driver and more than one operator

Even more often, when analyzing the freight transport process, activities related to the handling of shipping documents are omitted. During these activities, there may be direct contact between people or the possibility of infecting the surface of the documents. Therefore, it was also decided to prepare a scale for this criterion.

Table 15. Scale of hazards –potential infection depending on the type of document flow and driver involvement

Hazard score	Description
1	Contactless flow of documents. The driver remains in the cabin of the vehicle and has no contact with a potentially infected person. Fully electronic data exchange
2	The driver only provides the documents by placing them in the designated point
3	Direct contact of the driver with a potentially infected person and handing flow of documents
4	Direct contact of the driver with a potentially infected person and signing of documents in front of the recipient
5	Direct contact of the driver with a potentially infected person and exchange of documents of both parties or signing of documents by both parties

The last criterion was developed due to the risk of contamination during receipt (delivery) of the parcel or cargo.

Table 16. Scale of hazards – potential infection depending on the type of delivery point

Hazard score	Description
1	Contactless delivery to the door or to a point that does not require contact with the infrastructure
2	Non-contact delivery to a point that requires contact with the infrastructure but without human service
3	Delivery to a point that requires contact with the infrastructure and has a staff employed, while the delivery is collected by one person
4	Delivery to the recipient's hands and direct contact with a potentially infected recipient. The delivery is collected by a maximum of one person
5	Delivery to the recipient's hands and direct contact with a potentially infected recipient. The delivery is picked up by more than one person